

Prediction of Stroke Risk Within 7-Years Follow Up Using Machine Learning Models*

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Abstract— A stroke event occurs when blood supply to your brain is interrupted. Primary prevention relies on prompt prediction of a stroke. While currently there are several clinical risk scores, machine learning (ML) models seems to be more suitable tools for accurate prediction of stroke events. Therefore, this work focuses on the prediction of stroke within 7 years follow-up in patients who have not suffered from a stroke or TIA event at baseline. LightGBM (LGBM), Extreme Grading Boosting (XGBoost), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Decision Tree were employed in the getABI dataset, which includes 5,897 participants. The performance of models was calculated by Accuracy (ACC), Sensitivity (SENS), Specificity (SPE) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of each model. According to the comparison analysis's results, LGBM has been shown to be the most trustworthy algorithm, with accuracy 68 %. Moreover, sex, age, status of peripheral artery disease (PAD), history of myocardial infarction, angina pectoris, amputation and diabetes and pulse status of different arteries can be used as a simple and cost-effective way to predict stroke.

Clinical Relevance— A fatal medical emergency, stroke may be anticipated using artificial intelligence, and the sooner it is predicted, the more cerebrovascular disease occurrences can be avoided.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stroke event is occurred when the blood artery is blocked by a clot or ruptures. A stroke might include permanent brain damage, chronic disability, and even fatality. There are over 12.2 million new strokes each year. One in four people over age 25 will have a stroke in their lifetime worldwide [1]. Stroke is the second most common cause of death worldwide, accounting for 11.6% of fatalities in 2019 [2]. 1 in 6 deaths from cardiovascular disease was due to stroke in 2021 [3]. It is important to gain more insights about the risk indicators of stroke to predict it effectively on time.

In the study of Vodencarevic *et al.* [4], 384 patients with stroke were followed at 3 and 12 months after first event and then annually, in order to predict the stroke risk after 1 year follow-up. Based on multiple ML models, they achieved AUC of 70 % using as input the following features: housing

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circumstances, rehabilitative measures, age, high calorie diet, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy, number of family doctor's home visits, and patient's mental state. Another work predicts the long-term stroke in 2091 patients using 53 features including age, BMI and laboratory data. Accuracy values of stroke prediction at 1-year and 5-years were 85% and 78 %, respectively [5]. Moreover, the stroke was predicted in 3,254 patients by stacking method with accuracy 98 %. They used features such as age, gender, hypertension, BMI, heart disease history, smoking status, glucose level, ever married, work and residence type [6]. In addition, 90-day ischemic stroke occurrence was also predicted employing SVM, random forest, artificial neural network and a hybrid artificial neural network [7]. The achieved AUC by SVM was 94 % utilizing pre-admission and inpatient data and 97 % when the follow-up data were added. The results were based on the most 17 important features, which selected by extra-trees algorithm from a whole set of 206 variables.

We used ML algorithms to predict the risk of stroke within a 7-year follow-up in this study. The analyzed patients have not suffered from stroke or TIA at baseline. In the prediction were used 12 features, including history of specific comorbidities, demographics and data from the clinical procedure. The metrics were evaluated in order to assess the performance of ML models. The novel component of this study is the few and easy taken features from clinicians, which were utilized as indicators of impending stroke.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Data Description and Analysis

The German epidemiological trial on ankle brachial index - getABI cohort [8], which used in the analysis, contains 6,445 patients being 65 years or older. It includes demographics, medications, comorbidities, laboratory and clinical data. Various endpoints that are linked to cardiovascular disease and death in different follow-ups were also included. Our analysis was performed on 5,897 patients, excluding patients who suffered from stroke (289 patients) or transient ischemic attack (TIA) (255 patients) at baseline or those who had missing

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values in these events (14 samples). The final dataset was comprised of 12 independent variables, including history of comorbidities, sex, age and pulse status of different arteries, using feature selection technique. These features are presented in Table I with their statistics for the patient class and the healthy participant class.

TABLE I. DATA STATISTICS

Attributes	Mean value \pm SD / Percentage	
	Class 0	Class 1
Age	72.31 \pm 5.32	74.20 \pm 5.26
Sex	Male of 68.9 %, female of 31.8 %	Male of 46.0 %, female of 54.0%
Myocardial infarction History (baseline)	Yes: 8.4%, No:91.6%	Yes:6.1 %, No:93.9 %
Angina pectoris History (baseline)	Yes: 13.1 %, No: 86.9%	Yes:17.2 %, No:82.8 %
Amputation History (baseline)	Yes: 0.2, No: 99.8 %	Yes 0.5 %, No: 99.5 %
History of diabetes	Yes:23.3, No:76.7%	Yes:37.9%, No:62.1%
Peripheral Artery Disease Status	8 % symptomatic, 11.0 asymptomatic, 80.1 no/not known, 0.8 % media sclerosis	13.1 % symptomatic, 18.7 asymptomatic, 67.2 no/not known, 1.0 % media sclerosis
Pulse Status: Dorsalis Pedis Right Artery	74.5 % Easily palpable, 18.4 % weakly palpable, 7.1 % not palpable	65.0 % Easily palpable, 20.8 % weakly palpable, 14.2 % not palpable
Pulse Status: Tibialis Posterior Left Artery	67.5 % Easily palpable, 22.3 % weakly palpable, 10.2 % not palpable	53.3 % Easily palpable, 27.9 % weakly palpable, 18.8 % not palpable
Pulse Status: Tibialis Posterior Right Artery	67.7 % Easily palpable, 22.3 % weakly palpable, 10.0 % not palpable	58.9 % Easily palpable, 21.3 weakly palpable, 19.8 not palpable
Pulse Status: Popliteal Right Artery	67.3 % Easily palpable, 22.4 % weakly palpable, 10.3 % not palpable	61.4 % Easily palpable, 26.4 % weakly palpable, 12.2 % not palpable
Pulse Status: Femoralis Left Artery	90.9 % Easily palpable, 8.0 % weakly palpable, 1.2 % not palpable	87.3 % Easily palpable, 11.7 % weakly palpable, 1.0 % not palpable

B. Methodology

The workflow of the current work is comprised of the following stages. Data pre-processing and curation steps were applied, such as one-hot encoding and scaling, which were used for categorical and numeric features, respectively. Moreover, imputation technique was employed in order to handle the missing values. Feature selection was initially done manually, excluding medication and questionnaire data, resulting in 75 features left. From this set, the most 12 important features were selected by SelectKBest method (Table I). Moreover, unbalanced classes of target variable were subjected to Random-under-sampler approach, as the number of patients in class 1 (198 patients) is significantly lower than the number of patients in class 0 (5,699). 10-fold cross-validation was used to train the models extracting mean values of performance metrics.

III. RESULTS

The effectiveness of each ML model was evaluated by computing the metrics after training and testing using 10-fold cross-validation. Table II displays the outcomes of each model. The top predictive model, LGBM, was selected based on accuracy, outperforming the other classifiers in terms of metrics. It achieved accuracy of 67.93 %, sensitivity of 60.20 %, and specificity 68.48% and AUC of 63.19 %. In contrast, the SVM performs the worst values of accuracy, sensitivity and specificity. The outcomes further demonstrate that the dataset's balanced classes are indicated by the low-value difference between sensitivity and specificity.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE METRICS OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

Metrics/ Models	ACC (%)	SENS (%)	SPE (%)	AUC (%)
XGBoost	60.91	57.86	68.11	61.22
LGBM	67.93	60.20	68.48	63.19
SVM	59.04	56.60	59.22	62.07
Decision Tree	65.47	56.54	66.11	56.84

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Stroke is an important event that requires early prevention and immediate treatment. For this reason, the prediction of stroke after years of follow-up makes it possible to prevent it following the appropriate interventions. The innovation of this work lies in the use of 12 simple features that are easily recorded in the clinical practice, compared to the state of the art studies, which used features that are confirmed risk factors for stroke prediction. The LightGBM predicts stroke within 7 years follow-up in patients without history of stroke or TIA at baseline, achieving 68 % accuracy.

REFERENCES

- [1] "WSO_Global_Stroke_Fact_Sheet.pdf." Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.world-stroke.org/assets/downloads/WSO_Global_Stroke_Fact_Sheet.pdf
- [2] V. L. Feigin *et al.*, "Global, regional, and national burden of stroke and its risk factors, 1990–2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019," *Lancet Neurol.*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 795–820, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(21)00252-0.
- [3] CDC, "Stroke Facts | cdc.gov," Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cdc.gov/stroke/facts.htm>
- [4] A. Vodencarevic *et al.*, "Prediction of Recurrent Ischemic Stroke Using Registry Data and Machine Learning Methods: The Erlangen Stroke Registry," *Stroke*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 2299–2306, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1161/STROKEAHA.121.036557.
- [5] V. Abedi *et al.*, "Prediction of Long-Term Stroke Recurrence Using Machine Learning Models," *J. Clin. Med.*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. 1286, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/jcm10061286.
- [6] E. Dritsas and M. Trigka, "Stroke Risk Prediction with Machine Learning Techniques," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 13, p. 4670, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22134670.
- [7] C.-H. Lin *et al.*, "Evaluation of Machine Learning Methods to Stroke Outcome Prediction Using a Nationwide Disease Registry," *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.*, vol. 190, p. 105381, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2020.105381.
- [8] getABI Study group, "getABI: German epidemiological trial on ankle brachial index for elderly patients in family practice to detect peripheral arterial disease, significant marker for high mortality," *VASA Z. Gefasskrankheiten*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 241–248, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1024/0301-1526.31.4.241.